

A Study on the Factors Influence on Switching Behaviour of Consumer in Trincomalee District

Special Reference to Carbonated Soft Drinks

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Abstract

Customer switching behaviour damages market share and profitability of service firms yet has remained virtually un-explored in the marketing literature (Susan M. Keaveney, Apr 1995). Meanwhile customers expect the marketers to be aware on their newly emerging needs and wants. Therefore, there is a need for marketers to address the switching behaviour of customers. But, in Sri Lankan context it remains unclear of whether customer switching behaviour is actually acting in customers' mind on selection of any product and services. This is a problem for contemporary marketers in meeting the growing customer expectations for switching issues. This problem is analyzed in this study. This study is carried out in the Carbonated Soft Drink Market with special reference to Trincomalee District. Further, this research seems to be important to the public, business people, professionals and academics and researchers. Researcher applies quantitative methodology, and questionnaires would be used for data collection.

1. INTRODUCTION

Customer switching behaviour can be seen as serious risk to the wealth and profitability of the firm. At present marketers are motivated to address the customer switching behaviour in order to ensure long-term relationships with their customers. Meanwhile customers have become more mobile and better informed than ever before, are increasingly able to get precisely what they want, when they want it, and at the price, they are willing to pay. To meet these exacting desires, new and different products and services appear unceasingly in customers' aspect. Due to these reasons, the marketing environment has become more competitive. Therefore, the manufactures implement many strategies to create and retain customers for their product in the competitive marketing environment.

Therefore concept of customer switching behaviour has become popular among the general public, business people, professionals and academic; and has gain universal recognition. As a consequence contemporary marketing managers attempt to address the customer switching behaviour. Thus, knowledge on customer switching behaviour is widely known and practiced in most of the organizations in particular in carbonated soft drink market. But, in Sri Lanka, there is a empirical gap of whether customer switching behaviour has addressed in carbonated soft drink market. This problem is examined in this study. This research is significant to customers, marketers and shareholders. Furthermore, this research adds new knowledge to the scientific community. Researcher employs quantitative methodology and questionnaire method for this research.

This chapter provides the introduction to the study. First it presents the background for the areas of study and followed by problem identification. Then it presents research questions, research objectives, and purpose of the research. Next section covers scope of the study. Afterwards it presents significance and it explains justification for the study followed by brief explanation to research methodology. Finally it outlines research limitations.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Consumer Behaviour and Customer Switching Behaviour

2.1.1 Consumer Behaviour

The field of consumer behaviour is the study of individuals, groups, or organizations and the processes they use to select, secure, use, and dispose of products, services, experiences, or ideas to satisfy needs and the impacts that these process have on the consumer and society. This view of the consumer behaviour is boarder than the traditional one, which focused much more on the buyer and the immediate antecedents and consequences of the purchasing process. This view will lead to examine indirect influences on consumption decision as well as consequences that involve more than the purchaser and seller. Hence, all the marketing decision and regulations are based on assumptions about consumer behaviour (Del I Hawkins, Roger J Best, Kenneth A Coney, and Amit Mookerjee 2007).

2.1.2 Postpurchase Process, Customer Satisfaction, Dissatisfaction, and Customer Switching Behaviour

Below image illustrates the relationship among the postpurchase processes. As the figure indicates, some purchases are followed by a phenomenon called postpurchase dissonances. This occurs when a consumer doubts the wisdom of a purchase he or she has made. Other purchases are followed by nonuse. This means the consumer keep or return the products without using it. However, most purchase are followed by product use, even if post purchase dissonances is present. Product use often requires the disposition of the product package or the product itself. During and after use, the purchase process and the product are evaluated by the customers. Whereas, unsatisfactory evolutions may produce complains by those consumers, and the customer switching behaviour can be played in this stage. Appropriate response by the firm may reverse the initial dissatisfaction among those who complained. The result of all these processes is a final level of satisfaction, which in turn can result in loyal, committed customer, one who is willing to repurchase, or a customer who switches brands or discontinues using the product category.

Post Purchase Consumer Behaviour

3. Theoretical Framework

The conceptualization framework shows a clear picture of the research. This Conceptual framework is use to indicate the relationship between the variables, which are involved in this study.

Based on literature survey following conceptual framework was developed. This conceptual framework establishes link between marketing mix variable, personal factor and customer switching behaviour

(Source: Formed for this Research)

4. Research Methodology

The aim of this research is to explore the switching behaviour of people in Trincomalee district. This study is based on primary data and secondary data. Primary data collected by issuing questionnaire and secondary data collected from past research papers, literature, reports, and internet. Convenience sampling technique was carried out to collect the data from people. 200 participants were conveniently selected from Trincomalee district and questionnaires were issued to them. . For this study purpose, only three variables were analyzed such as marketing mix, personal factor and psychographic factor to carry out the study on switching behaviour. Where as, marketing mix and consumers' personal factor, were considered as independent variables whereas switching behaviour was considered as depended variable.

5. Analysis and discussions

5.1. Personal information of respondents

In this section, the analysis on personal information conducts on the information collected from 200 respondents and their age, gender, civil status, occupation, educational qualification, number of members in their family, monthly family income, and religion were analyzed.

5.1.1. Age

Age distribution of respondents of represented by Age distribution five classes. of respondents between 15 to 20.5% of founded

<i>Age Group</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent (%)</i>
15-20	20	10.0
21-30	80	40.0
31-40	41	20.5
41-45	35	17.5
above 45	24	12.0
Total	200	100.0

Source-Survey data

of age, 17.5% of respondents were found between 41 to 45 years old, and remaining 12% represents above 45 years.

pattern of the this research is the sample size of 200. was categorized into Among the sample, 10% were found to be 20 years old, 40% were 21 to 30 years of age, respondents were between 31 to 40 years

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent (%)</i>
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5.1.2. Gender

The gender distribution of the respondents of the Trincomalee has been represented by the sample size of 200. Out of these 200 respondents 50.5% of the respondents were female and remaining 49.5% were male.

Male	99	49.5
Female	101	50.5
Total	200	100

Source-Survey data

<i>Educational Qualification</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Postgraduate	27	13.5
Graduate Studies	60	30.0
G.C.E A/L	92	46.0
G.C.E O/L	17	8.5

5.1.3.

Educational Qualification

The educational qualification of the respondents for this research is represented by the sample size of 200. The educational qualifications of respondents were classified into five categories in the questionnaire.

Out of 200 respondents 13.5% of the respondents had post graduate qualification, and 30% of the respondents had a bachelor degree, 46% of the respondents had the qualification of up to A/L, 8.5% of them had completed their Ordinary Level examination but not Advance level, and and where remaining 2% of them were found under the category of up to grade 8.

Up to grade 8	4	2.0
Total	200	100.0

Source-Survey data

5.2. Research information

5.2.1. Reliability test of data

Cronbach's alpha reliability method was employed to confirm the reliability of data in the context of study problem. These results indicate that these factors are more than 0.6 therefore it reveals that variables used in this study were highly reliable.

Reliability test of data

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha coefficient</i>
Marketing Mix	0.833
Personal Factor	0.877

Source: Survey data

5.2.2. Descriptive analysis on Marketing Mix

5.2.2.1. Product

The dimension of product has high influence on switching decision of customers (mean value is 3.95). In addition to this most of the switching customers have merely same opinion regarding product (standard deviation is 0.874).

The dimension of product measured via eleven indicators such as brand name, taste, different size, quality, favourable smell, safety to health, nutrition, packaging, product variety, product modification, and package design. The indicators of Brand name, taste, different size, quality, favourable smell, safety to health, nutrition, packaging,

product variety, product modification, and package design got the mean values of 4.03, 4.21, 3.98, 4.4, 3.86, 3.82, 3.52, 3.96, 3.99, 3.96, and 3.82 respectively.

Around 75% of switching customers agree that purchased brand name is very popular than the competitors' brand name and around 50% to 58% of switching customers agree that the product taste, product and package size, its smell, their health oriented consumption, packaging of soft drink, varieties of soft drinks in same brand, product modification, and package design were induced their switching tendency.

Indicators in Product	Mean	SD	Scales									
			Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree	
			Fq	%	Fq	%	Fq	%	Fq	%	Fq	%
Brand Name	4.03	0.662	3	1.8	2	1.2	10	6	124	74.3	28	16.8
Taste	4.21	0.693	1	0.6	3	1.8	11	6.6	97	58.1	55	32.9
Different Size	3.98	0.854	4	2.4	4	2.4	26	15.6	90	53.9	43	25.7
Quality	4.40	0.777	96	57.5	43	25.7	27	16.2	1	0.6	--	--
Favourable Smell	3.86	0.950	7	4.2	7	4.2	25	15	91	54.4	37	22.2
Safety to Health	3.82	0.873	2	1.2	13	7.8	30	18	90	53.9	32	19.2
Nutrition	3.52	1.246	13	7.8	24	14.4	38	22.8	47	28.1	45	26.9
Packaging	3.96	0.838	2	1.2	7	4.2	29	17.4	87	52.1	42	25.1
Product Variety	3.99	0.868	2	1.2	9	5.4	24	14.4	85	50.9	47	28.1
Product Modification	3.96	0.901	3	1.8	9	5.4	26	15.6	83	49.7	46	27.5
Design	3.82	0.953	5	3	14	8.4	21	12.6	93	55.7	34	20.4
Total	3.96	0.874										

(Source: Survey data)

5.2.2.2. Price

The dimension of price has high influence on switching decision of customers (mean value is 3.79). In addition to this most of the switching customers have merely somewhat different opinion regarding price (standard deviation is 0.945).

The price as a dimension its composed by four indicators such as price, discount facility, credit terms, and payment period. The indicators of price, discount facility, credit terms, and payment period got the mean values of 4.24, 3.56, 3.62, and 3.74 respectively.

Around 45% of switching customers strongly disagree about higher price of the product and only around 38% to 45% of switching customers agree the marketers are offering them discount facility, credit terms, and payment period. However, most of switching customers have somewhat different judgment regarding the inducement of their switching tendency due to the price offers, discount facilities that offers by marketers, availability of credit terms, and flexible payment period. (SD are 0.823, 1.027, 0.998, and 0.931 respectively).

<i>Indicators in Price</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Scales</i>									
			<i>Strongly Disagree</i>		<i>Disagree</i>		<i>Neutral</i>		<i>Agree</i>		<i>Strongly Agree</i>	
			<i>Fq</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Fq</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Fq</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Fq</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>Fq</i>	<i>%</i>
Price	4.24	0.823	75	44.9	62	37.1	26	15.6	3	1.8	1	0.6
Discount Facility	3.56	1.027	7	4.2	18	10.8	44	26.3	70	41.9	28	16.8
Credit Terms	3.62	0.998	5	3	15	9	51	30.5	63	37.7	33	19.8
Payment Period	3.74	0.931	3	1.8	13	7.8	42	25.1	75	44.9	34	20.4
Total	3.79	0.945										

(Source: Survey data)

5.2.2.3. Place

The dimension of place has high influence on switching decision of customers (mean value is 4.13). In addition to this most of the switching customers have nearly same opinion regarding place (standard deviation is 0.781).

The average value for place was analyzed with the composition of six indicators such as product availability, location, assortments or quantities, channel of distribution, coverage area, and sellers' recommendations.

The indicators of availability, location, assortments / quantities, channel, coverage area, and sellers' recommendations having the mean values of 4.23, 4.16, 4.11, 4.27, 4.19, and 3.85 respectively. Around 45% to 55% of switching customers agree that the product availability, location, assortments / quantities, channel, coverage area, and sellers' recommendations empower their switching decision. However, most of switching customers have somewhat different argument regarding their switching decision was induced by sellers (SD is 0.922).

Indicators in Place	Mean	SD	Scales									
			Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree	
			Fq	%	Fq	%	Fq	%	Fq	%	Fq	%
Availability	4.23	0.742	2	1.2	4	2.4	7	4.2	95	56.9	59	35.3
Location	4.16	0.755	1	0.6	6	3.6	12	7.2	94	56.3	54	32.3
Assortments / Quantities	4.11	0.753	-	-	7	4.2	18	10.8	92	55.1	50	29.9
Channel	4.27	0.672	1	0.6	1	0.6	12	7.2	91	54.5	62	37.1
Coverage Area	4.19	0.843	1	0.6	8	4.8	16	9.6	75	44.9	67	40.1
Sellers Recommendations	3.85	0.922	4	2.4	13	7.8	22	13.2	93	55.7	35	21
Total	4.13	0.781										

(Source: Survey data)

5.2.2.4. Promotion

The promotion as a dimension has high-level influence on customers' switching tendency (mean value is 4.08) and switching customers also have nearly same opinion

regarding promotion however, there are also somewhat different opinion about influence of promotion on their switching tendency (Standard Deviation is 0.789).

Table 5.18 Promotion analysis for switching customers

Indicators in Promotion	Mean	SD	Scales									
			Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree	
			Fq	%	Fq	%	Fq	%	Fq	%	Fq	%
Advertisements	4.29	0.695	-	-	4	2.4	11	6.6	85	50.9	67	40.1
Sales Promotion	4.08	0.843	2	1.2	8	4.8	17	10.2	88	52.7	52	31.1
Public Relation	3.96	0.798	3	1.8	4	2.4	26	15.6	97	58.1	37	22.2
Sales Forces	4.00	0.821	2	1.2	7	4.2	23	13.8	92	55.1	43	25.7
Total	4.08	0.789										

(Source: Survey data)

The advertisements, sales promotion, public relation, and sales forces are the indicators of promotion in this research. Hence, it takes 4.29, 4.08, 3.96, and 4.00 as a mean value for each indicator. Around 50% to 60% of the switching customers confirm that the above indicators induce their switching tendency.

5.2.3. Descriptive analysis on Personal Factors

The influence of age, gender and education on switching tendency covered in personal factor influence. The personal factor as a dimension of personal factor has moderate-level influence on switching decision of customers (mean value is 3.15) and most of switching customers have greater degree of disagreement with the influences of personal factor on their switching behaviour (Standard Deviation is 1.142).

Table 5.20 Personal factor analysis for switching customers

Indicators in Personal Factor	Mean	SD	Scales									
			Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree	
			Fq	%	Fq	%	Fq	%	Fq	%	Fq	%
Age	3.17	1.283	26	15.6	25	15	33	19.8	61	36.5	22	13.2
Gender	3.21	1.197	19	11.4	30	18	3	19.8	67	40.1	18	10.8
Education	3.04	1.163	19	11.4	38	22.8	41	24.6	55	32.9	14	8.4

Total	3.157	1.142
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(Source: Survey data)

Only 25% to 40% of switching customers confirm that all of above indicators induce their switching tendency. Hence, standard deviation for all indicators denotes that, most of switching customers perceive that, there is a disparity between their personal factors and switching behaviour.

6. Conclusion and Recommendation

When Analyzing the age structure of the respondents, out of 167 switching respondents 60.5% of them were between 21-40, and they have been expressed that there is a high-level of customer switching behaviour in their carbonated soft-drink purchase and also uttered high level of influence by marketers' marketing mix offering and having moderate influence by their personal factor on their switching tendency. Because, these age group highly correlated with their personal characteristics and can easily be attracted by marketing stimulus.

12% of the respondents were in the age range of between 15-20 years old, that they perceived moderate level of switching tendency in their purchase with moderate influence of personal and high marketing mix influence; However, all the mean values are somewhat lower than others' mean values as this age group are depending on others' decision-making power with limited purchasing power.

The switching customers who are between 41-45 years of age have moderate level of switching tendency in their soft-drink purchase with moderate level of influence by their personal and higher level of influence by marketers' market offerings. The customers who are above 45 years of old have moderate level influence of customer personal factor; therefore, this age group perceives moderate-level of customer switching behaviour.

Out of the 167 switching respondents, 49.1% were males and 50.9% were females. While males perceive moderate level of switching behaviour (mean is 3.49), females perceive high level switching behaviour (mean is 3.53) in their carbonated soft drink

purchase. The contribution for male's moderate level of influence comes from high-level influence of marketing mix (mean is 3.93) and moderate influence of consumer personal (2.95) factor. Hence, the contribution for female's high level of influence comes from high-level influence of marketing mix offerings (mean is 4.05) and moderate level influence of consumers' personal (mean is 3.07).

The reason for these tendencies is, females are easily attracted by marketers' offering than males, they used to care about their personal factor such as age, culture, etc before who take the switching or purchasing decision.

In concern with educational qualification influence on customers' switching decision, 41.9% of switching customers had the qualification above Bachelor degree, and have been expressed a high-level of switching tendency on their repurchase of carbonated soft drink the contribution for this higher degree of switching tendencies are higher-level influence of marketing mix (4.07 for graduates and 3.98 for post graduates) and moderate level influence of personal factor (2.98 for graduates and 3.22 for post graduates) on their switching tendency.

While other 46.1% of A/L switching customers perceive moderate-level of customer switching tendency (3.49) on their repurchase of carbonated soft drink. Moreover, they perceived higher-level influence of marketing mix (3.95) and moderate-level influence of their personal factor variables (3.02). The reason for this tendency is, this group has moderate-level of educational background, therefore, they assess marketing mix offering with their psychographic factor of perception but with some limited extent, and then finally they switched their brands.

The educational qualification who has below O/L (12%), recognize moderate influence of switching tendency on their repurchase of carbonated soft drink with moderate influence of consumers' personal and high influence of marketing mix offering on their switching tendency. As these groups have low-level educational background, they easily attracted by marketers' offering and moderately considering their personal factor influences.

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